

IN MEMORIAM

Prof. Dr. Ivan Milošević (1948 – 2021)

Prof. Dr. Ivan Milošević was born on 13th of September 1948 in Novi Sad, Serbia. He completed his primary and secondary education in Kotor and graduated from the Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, University of Sarajevo in 1974. In the same year he was employed at IBMI - Podgorica, OOUR Department of Experimental Biology and Medicine - Kotor, Laboratory for Brain Research, later the Institute of Marine Biology, University of Montenegro, Laboratory for Neurobiology and Ecophysiology.

In January 1986, Prof. Milošević defended his master's thesis "Biogenic monoamines and locomotor behavior of the gastropod *Aplysia depilans* L.", on department of Neurobiology, at the Center for Multidisciplinary Studies, University of Belgrade. In June 1989, he defended his doctoral dissertation entitled "Contribution to the anatomical and biochemical organization of gastropod behavior" at the Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics, University of Sarajevo.

Prof. Milošević was elected a Research Associate in January 1990 at the Institute of Marine Biology, University of Montenegro. He acquired the title of docent for the subject "Comparative Physiology" at the Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics, University of Montenegro, by election in June 1994. He was elected a Senior Scientific Associate in June 1995, while an Associate Professor of "Comparative Physiology" was elected in June 2000. In February 2001, he was elected Scientific Advisor.

Aiming to improve and train for scientific research and exchange of experience gained in the field of neurobiology, he attended several work trainings in the country and abroad. Particularly interesting and meaningful was months-long stay of prof.

Milošević in Japan within the Kanagawa International Fisheries Training Center, supported by the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) during 1987.

Research interest of prof. Milošević was a neurophysiological aspect of studying different groups of organisms. He mainly conducted research aimed at determining the integrative activity of the central nervous system, as a basis for understanding the functional evolution of the organism and the behavioral process from the simplest invertebrates to humans. Prof. Milošević paid special attention to the application of oocytes and early embryos of marine invertebrates for testing and detailed study of pharmacological preparations as well as histochemical and cytological research of biogenic monoamines during embryogenesis of mollusks and echinoderms.

As manager or associate prof. Milošević realized several national and international projects, in which he achieved fruitful cooperation with scientific institutions in the country and abroad. Among the international projects, we should point out the

project "Electrophysiological evaluation of ecophysiological adaptations of the visual system of fish", which he managed in cooperation with the Institute for Information Transmission Problems of the Russian Academy of Sciences. Prof. Milošević carried out numerous working visits to institutions in Russia and for a long period he had joint projects with N.K. Koljtsov Institute of Developmental Biology of the Russian Academy of Sciences in Moscow and the scientific team of Dr. Gennady A. Buznikov, who is considered "the father of neurotransmitters as developmental signals". Long-term cooperation with Prof. Dr. Ljubiša Rakić, Academician of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts and the Biochemical Institute, Faculty of Medicine in Belgrade was continued after the retirement of prof. Milošević in 2015.

Prof. Milošević was lecturer in the frame of summer schools for biology students of the Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics from Sarajevo, Belgrade, Novi Sad, Banja Luka and Kragujevac. Also, he participated in the planning and preparation of experiments for master's and doctoral theses of postgraduates of the Center for Multidisciplinary Studies at the University of

Belgrade and Novi Sad. He has lectured in the subjects "Comparative Physiology", "Neurobiology with Ethology" and "Ecophysiology of Animals" from establishing of the Department of Biology, at the Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics of the University of Montenegro in Podgorica, until his retirement.

In his scientific research activity, prof. Milošević has published more than 80 papers in national and international scientific journals and symposia.

On 16th of March 2021, our collective has lost Prof. Dr. Ivan Milošević, Scientific Advisor of the Institute of Marine Biology and Associate Professor at the Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics of the University of Montenegro in retirement. He left us not only his valuable scientific and pedagogic work but also many precious memories. We will remember him as a good colleague, an excellent scientist, a good professor, always smiling and ready to help.

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